

NUMERICAL AND EXPERIMENTAL STUDIES ON THE
RESIN TRANSFER MOLD FILLING PROCESS

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ABSTRACT

A numerical simulation of mold filling process during resin transfer molding(RTM) was performed using the boundary element method(BEM). Experimental verification was also done. Darcy's law for porous media was employed along with mass conservation to construct the governing differential equation. Perturbation method was applied to transform the governing differential equation with variable viscosity into a form suitable for the boundary element method. The resulting Poisson equations were solved with boundary element technique. As the calculation domain changes due to the proceeding resin front, boundary nodes were rearranged for each time step. Results showed a good agreement with the experimental data for a rectangular mold. Numerical calculations were also performed for complicated geometries to illustrate the effectiveness of the current method.

Keywords: Boundary Element Method; Flow Analysis; Injection Molding; Perturbation Method; Resin Transfer Molding.

1. INTRODUCTION

The resin transfer molding (RTM) technique is widely being used for manufacturing large and thin structures such as radomes, wing skins, boat shells, panels, etc. In RTM, resin (mostly thermosets) is injected into a mold filled with reinforcing fibers (Fig.1). In many cases the reinforcement is in the form of cloth or mat. RTM yields structures with better mechanical properties than the ones laid up by hand. The productivity is also superior to the hand lay-up. One of the most important steps in RTM process is the design of the mold. Proper design of the mold is crucial for the resin flow and thus the fill time. Special care must be taken to prevent possible dry spots where resin is not reached. Therefore the analysis of resin flow in the mold is a very important task in designing the RTM processes. The prediction of the resin flow becomes essential for heated molds since the resin may gel before the mold

fills. Numerical and experimental analyses of resin filling in RTM process had been performed by Coulter and Guceri(1), Bruschke and Advani(2), and Lee et. al. (3). They employed the finite difference technique with boundary fitted coordinate system. Um and Lee (4) did numerical simulation of the mold filling process using the boundary element method. Their method yielded very fast and accurate results only for constant resin viscosity. In this study, the resin flow during RTM process was studied numerically by boundary element method. In order to obtain numerical solution, perturbation method was employed. To assess the validity of the numerical calculations, experiments were also performed.

2. GOVERNING EQUATIONS

In order to analyze the resin flow inside the resin transfer mold, the reinforcement was assumed to be a porous medium. Since in many cases the thickness is very small compared to the length or width, the flow through the reinforcement can be thought to be two dimensional. The mass conservation for the resin flow can be stated as

$$\nabla \cdot (\rho \vec{u}) = 0 \quad (1)$$

where ρ is the density of the resin and \vec{u} is the velocity vector. If we apply Darcy's law for porous media (5-6),

$$\vec{u} = -\frac{K}{\mu} \nabla p \quad (2)$$

where μ is the viscosity of the resin, K is the permeability of the reinforcement and p is the pressure. The permeability becomes a tensor if the reinforcement is anisotropic. For the simplicity it is assumed that the reinforcement is isotropic and thus the permeability is a scalar quantity. The formulation presented in this paper can easily be extended to account for the anisotropy. It is also assumed that the viscosity is not a function of the shear rate(i.e. Newtonian). For resin systems which shows highly non-Newtonian behavior, this assumption is not valid and viscosity-shear rate relationship such as power law must be employed.

If the density of the resin is constant (i.e., incompressible), Eqs.(1) and (2) can be combined to yield

$$\nabla \cdot [s(x,y)\nabla p] = 0 \quad (3)$$

where $s(x,y)=K/\mu$ and is a measure of fluidity (7). It is noted that s becomes a function of location as the resin viscosity varies for different positions. Therefore Eq.(3) has no fundamental solution in general (8).

The boundary conditions can be stated as follows (4)

$$\text{Mold Wall : } \partial p / \partial n = 0 \quad (4a)$$

$$\text{Resin Front : } p = 0 \quad (4b)$$

$$\text{Resin Inlet : } p = p_0 \quad \text{or} \quad \partial p / \partial n = q_0 \quad (4c)$$

where n represents the direction normal to the mold surface (see Fig.2).

3. NUMERICAL

In order to solve Eq.(3) along with boundary conditions (Eqs.4a-4c) for two dimensional geometry, boundary element method (BEM) is employed. By using BEM the effort in mesh generation as in numerical techniques such as finite element or finite difference methods can greatly be saved. However the fundamental solution required for boundary element analysis cannot be obtained for Eq.(3) as explained previously. Therefore the Eq.(3) must be solved in a iterative manner using perturbation method(8) and the resulting Poisson equations were solved using BEM.

3.1 Perturbation Method

If we define a new variable g as

$$g = \sqrt{s}p \quad (5)$$

Equation (3) becomes

$$\nabla^2 g + f(x,y)g = 0 \quad (6)$$

where

$$f(x,y) = \frac{|\nabla s|^2}{4s^2} - \frac{\nabla^2 s}{2s} \quad (7)$$

The boundary conditions can be transformed as

$$\text{Mold Wall : } \frac{\partial g}{\partial n} = \frac{1}{2s} \frac{\partial s}{\partial n} g \quad (8a)$$

$$\text{Resin Front : } g = 0 \quad (8b)$$

$$\text{Resin Inlet : } g = \sqrt{s}p_0 \quad \text{or} \quad \frac{\partial g}{\partial n} = \frac{1}{2s} \frac{\partial s}{\partial n} g + \sqrt{s}q_0 \quad (8c)$$

In order to apply the perturbation method, Eq.(6) is rewritten as

$$\nabla^2 g + \varepsilon r(x,y)g = 0 \quad 0 < \varepsilon < 1 \quad (9)$$

where

$$r(x, y) = \frac{1}{\varepsilon} f(x, y) \quad (10)$$

If we assume the solution of Eq.(9) in a series form as

$$g = \sum_{m=0}^{\infty} g_m \varepsilon^m \quad (11)$$

and substitute Eq.(11) into Eq.(9), we have

$$\nabla^2 g_0 + \sum_{m=1}^{\infty} \varepsilon^m (\nabla^2 g_m + r g_{m-1}) = 0 \quad (12)$$

Therefore the following series of differential equations along with the boundary conditions are obtained(8)

$$\nabla^2 g_0 = 0 \quad (13)$$

Boundary Conditions : Eqs.(8a-8c)

$$\nabla^2 g_m + r g_{m-1} = 0 \quad m = 1, 2, 3, \dots \quad (14)$$

Boundary Conditions : $\partial g / \partial n = 0$ or $g = 0$

Equation (13) is a Laplace equation and Eq.(14) are Poisson equations with source term. These equations can be solved numerically using the boundary element method. Once the values of the functions g_m are known, the value of g can be evaluated by Eq.(11). The number of functional evaluation depends on the convergence of the series (Eq.11). In this study, satisfactory convergence ($|g_m| / \sum_{i=1}^{m-1} g_i < 0.02$) was obtained usually after $m=2$.

3.2 Boundary Element Formulation

In order to formulate the boundary element equations, Eq.(14) was multiplied by weighting function g_m^* and was integrated over the calculation domain to yield(9)

$$\int_{\Omega} (\nabla^2 g_m + r g_{m-1}) g_m^* d\Omega = \int_{\Gamma_2} (h_m - \bar{h}_m) g_m^* d\Gamma - \int_{\Gamma_1} (g_m - \bar{g}_m) h_m^* d\Gamma \quad (15a)$$

$$h_m = \frac{\partial g_m}{\partial n} \quad (15b)$$

$$h_m^* = \frac{\partial g_m^*}{\partial n} \quad (15c)$$

where Ω is flow domain, Γ_1 and Γ_2 are flow boundaries with essential and natural condition,

respectively, and g_m^* is the weighting function. \bar{g}_m and \bar{h}_m are known values of g_m and h_m .

If we apply Green's theorem to the left hand side of Eq.(15a),

$$\int_{\Omega} (\nabla^2 g_m^*) g_m d\Omega + \int_{\Omega} (r g_{m-1}) g_m^* d\Omega = - \int_{\Gamma_2} \bar{h}_m g_m^* d\Gamma - \int_{\Gamma_1} h_m g_m^* d\Gamma + \int_{\Gamma_2} g_m h_m^* d\Gamma + \int_{\Gamma_1} \bar{g}_m h_m^* d\Gamma \quad (16)$$

The weighting function g_m^* is the fundamental solution of the Laplace equation. Equation (16) gives (9)

$$c^i g_m^i + \int_{\Omega} (r g_{m-1}) g_m^* d\Omega + \int_{\Gamma} g_m h_m^* d\Gamma = \int_{\Gamma} g_m^* h_m d\Gamma \quad (17)$$

where c^i is a geometric constant. If the boundary is smooth, c^i is 1/2 (9). If we divide the boundary into n boundary elements and apply Eq.(17), the following equation is obtained

$$c^i g_m^i + \sum_{\Omega_e} \int_{\Omega_e} (r g_{m-1}) g_m^* d\Omega + \sum_{j=1}^n \int_{\Gamma_j} g_m h_m^* d\Gamma = \sum_{j=1}^n \int_{\Gamma_j} g_m^* h_m d\Gamma \quad (18)$$

where Γ_j represents each boundary element. Ω_e denotes each subregion for numerical integration.

Equation (18) can be rewritten in a matrix form as

$$c^i g_m^i + B_i + \sum_{j=1}^n H_{ij} = \sum_{j=1}^n G_{ij} \quad (19)$$

where

$$B_i = \sum_{\Omega_e} \int_{\Omega_e} (r g_{m-1}) g_m^* d\Omega \quad (20a)$$

$$H_{ij} = \int_{\Gamma_j} g_m h_m^* d\Gamma \quad (20b)$$

$$G_{ij} = \int_{\Gamma_j} g_m^* h_m d\Gamma \quad (20c)$$

Unknown g and $\partial g / \partial n$ on the boundary are calculated by using Eq.(19). Once the unknown values are obtained along the boundary, g and $\partial g / \partial n$ inside the domain can be calculated (9). The pressure and pressure gradient can be calculated from the known values of g and $\partial g / \partial n$ by Eq.(5).

The interpolating function required in Eq.(18) can be either constant (constant boundary element), linear (linear boundary element) or quadratic (quadratic boundary element). In this study, the linear boundary element was selected for the numerical calculations for its accuracy

and relative simplicity. In order to solve Poisson equation with BEM, integration over the domain (see Eq.18) must be evaluated. For the numerical integration, the whole mold cavity was divided into subregions beforehand.

3.3 Node Relocation

At each time step, the flow of the resin inside the mold is regarded as quasi-steady. Therefore the new location of the resin front is determined by

$$\vec{S}(t + \delta t) = \vec{S}(t) + \vec{u} \delta t = \vec{S}(t) - \frac{K}{\mu} \nabla p \cdot \delta t \quad (21)$$

where \vec{S} denotes the displacement of each node. The distance between each node newly located by Eq.(21) becomes irregular. In order to enhance the accuracy of the numerical calculation, nodes are rearranged to have uniform distances between neighboring nodes.

When nodes are advanced by Eq.(21) some nodes close to the mold surface may move out of the solid wall. Wang et al. (7,10) solved this problem by relocating the nodes using mass conservation and orthogonality condition on the wall. Coulter and Guceri (1) reassigned nodes by applying the no-slip condition if the velocity near the wall was larger than a preset velocity while the orthogonality condition was applied if the velocity is smaller. In this study, new node was located at the intersection between the solid wall and the line drawn between the node at calculation steps, $\vec{S}(t)$ and $\vec{S}(t+\delta t)$ (see Fig.3).

Flow through thin mold cavity known as Hele-Shaw flow (7) is encountered in the injection molding process. The governing equation for the flow has the same form as the flow through a porous medium. In this case the parameter s in Eq.3 is related to the gap thickness b as (7)

$$s = K / \mu = b^3 / 3\mu \quad (22)$$

Therefore the variation in the gap thickness of thin mold leads to an equivalent effect as the variation in s for the flow through porous media.

4. EXPERIMENTAL

Mold filling tests were performed to evaluate the validity of the numerical result. The experiments were done with an apparatus shown in Fig.4 . The mold consists of two plates with gap thickness varying linearly from one edge to another. In order to observe the shape of the resin front, the top plate was made of transparent glass. Resin inlet was located at the center of the mold. Silicone oil ($\mu = 34.9$ Pa·sec at 16°C) was used as the resin. As the experiment started the resin was pressurized in the resin reservoir with N₂ gas. The valve between the mold and the resin reservoir was opened to allow the resin to flow through the gap. The pressure at the resin inlet was monitored with a pressure transducer. The pictures of the resin

front were taken with a camera at an arbitrary time interval. From these pictures the location of the resin front at each time step was obtained.

5. RESULTS

Tests were performed for a square mold (20cm by 20cm) (Fig.5). Inlet pressure variation as a function of time is shown in Fig.6. Inlet radius was 0.575 cm and the gap thickness varied linearly from 0.035 cm to 0.085 cm in one direction (see Fig.5). The observed location of the resin front as a function of time is given in Fig.7a. In Fig.7b the results from the numerical calculation for the same conditions are presented. As can be seen, good agreement was found between the numerical and the experimental results.

Next, numerical calculations were performed for two different mold geometries to demonstrate the effectiveness of the current numerical scheme. Viscosity of the resin was 40Pa·sec. The first run was made for a square mold (20cm x 20cm). Inlet width was 5.66 cm and inlet resin pressure was 1.0 MPa. The gap thickness changed linearly from 0.02 cm to 0.04 cm. The shape of the calculated resin fronts for different times are shown in Fig.8. An L-shape mold cavity was selected for the second run (Fig.9). Other conditions were same as the first run. The result of the numerical calculation is shown in Fig.9.

6. CONCLUDING REMARKS

In this study the boundary element technique together with the perturbation method was employed to study the mold filling process in RTM. A computer code was developed for the numerical simulation of the resin flow. As can be seen from the results, the agreement between the calculation and the experiments was good. The code can also be applied in the analyses of injection mold filling processes because of the similarity between injection molding and RTM. The BEM analysis in this study gave accurate numerical results in relatively short computing time compared with the control volume methods such as finite element method or finite difference method mainly due to the simplification in node generation. Due to the simplicity in the node generation, current method can be easily applied to molds with complicated geometries.

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FIGURE 1. Schematic of the resin transfer molding process.

FIGURE 2. Definition sketch.

FIGURE 3. Node relocation scheme.

FIGURE 4. Schematic of the experimental apparatus: experimental set-up.

FIGURE 5. Schematic of the experimental apparatus: mold assembly.

FIGURE 6. Changes in the inlet pressure as a function of time.

a)

b)

FIGURE 7. Locations of the resin front for different times (6, 35, 90, 152, 192, 206, 246 sec respectively): a) experimental result; b) numerical result.

FIGURE 8. Result of mold filling simulation for a diverging-converging mold. Location of the resin front as a function of time.

FIGURE 9. Result of mold filling simulation for an L-shape mold. Location of the resin front as a function of time.